

LEXICO-SEMANTIC DIFFERENTIATION OF THE LEXEMES “GUEST” AND “CLIENT” IN CONTEMPORARY KOREAN LINGUOCULTURE

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Abstract. This article examines the lexico-semantic differentiation of the lexemes 손님 [sonnim] “honored guest” and 고객님 [gogaengnim] “honored client” in contemporary Korean linguoculture. The study reveals that differences in cultural contexts and social situations determine the choice of one lexeme over the other in communicative acts. A comparative analysis is conducted on their domains of usage, stylistic nuances, and pragmatic connotations. Particular attention is given to the influence of traditional Korean values—such as hospitality, respect for guests, and etiquette—reflected in proverbs and idiomatic expressions, as well as to modern commercial and service communication standards. The research materials include examples from both spoken and written language, as well as data from online communication. The study concludes that the use of these lexemes reflects deeply rooted Korean cultural perceptions of social roles and the pragmatics of interpersonal communication.

Keywords: guest, client, Korean linguoculture, lexico-semantic differentiation.

Introduction. In contemporary Korean linguoculture, particular interest is drawn to the lexical-semantic differentiation between two closely related concepts—“honored guest” (손님 [sonnim]) and “honored client” (고객님 [gogaengnim]). This distinction reflects deeply rooted traditions and the evolving pragmatic demands of modern communication. Understanding the nuanced differences between these lexemes is important for both theoretical linguistics and practical applications in intercultural communication and Korean language education.

The aim of this study is to identify and analyze the lexical-semantic distinctions between the lexemes 손님 [sonnim] (“honored guest”) and 고객님 [gogaengnim] (“honored client”) within the framework of contemporary Korean linguoculture. To achieve this goal, the following objectives were established:

- To examine the etymological and semantic features of the lexemes 손님 [sonnim] (“honored guest”) and 고객님 [gogaengnim] (“honored client”);
- To conduct a comparative analysis of their spheres of usage;
- To determine the influence of traditional and modern Korean cultural values on the choice of lexeme in communication.

The relevance of this research lies in the fact that the differentiation between 손님 [sonnim] (“honored guest”) and 고객님 [gogaengnim] (“honored client”) reflects not only structural characteristics of the Korean language but also fundamental cultural attitudes manifested in present-day communicative practices.

The issue of lexical-semantic differentiation is a focus of ongoing linguistic research, particularly in the context of language-culture interaction. Topics such as semantic differentiation,

pragmatic functions, and cultural markedness of Korean lexical units have been repeatedly addressed in our prior studies.

Special attention has been devoted to the analysis of lexemes associated with the concept of “guest,” including their semantic variability, metaphorical and metonymic motivations, as well as their reflection in Korean proverbs and idioms (Kim, 2024). Other works on linguocultural analysis have considered aspects such as the semantics and pragmatics of address terms, euphemisms, culturally significant lexical oppositions, and word-formation patterns (Kim et al., 2023a).

Moreover, culturally conditioned semantic fields and conceptual domains have been identified as underlying the function of lexemes such as “century-long guest,” “night guest,” and “occasional guest” (Kim et al., 2023b). Within the framework of comparative typology between Russian and Korean, the functional-semantic potential of the lexeme “guest” has also been studied, including its connection to politeness strategies and speech etiquette in both historical and modern contexts (Zhinkin, 1998).

Despite the thematic scope of existing studies, the lexical-semantic and cultural-pragmatic differentiation between 손님 [sonnim] (“honored guest”) and 고객님 [gogaengnim] (“honored client”) has not yet been the subject of a separate, comprehensive analysis. The present study seeks to fill this gap through an in-depth examination of these lexemes in the context of traditional and modern sociocultural realities of Korean society. Research materials include proverbs, idioms, and examples from oral and written language, as well as internet sources (e.g., forums, websites, social media) (ZDNet Korea, n.d.; Naver Blog, n.d.; Select from User Blog, n.d.).

Lexical-semantic differentiation refers to the process of distinguishing lexemes based on meaning and usage conditions, taking into account pragmatic, stylistic, and cultural factors. For its analysis, key linguistic concepts such as lexeme, semantics, and pragmatics must be employed, as they allow for a comprehensive understanding of how language units function in discourse.

A lexeme is defined as a unit of the lexicon that encompasses all grammatical forms of a word and carries a stable meaning (Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary, 1990). Semantics investigates the meanings of these units, their internal structures, and interrelations within the language’s lexical system (Kuznetsova, 2004). Pragmatics, in turn, examines how linguistic expressions function in actual communicative situations, considering the speaker’s intentions, the speech context, and the social roles of the participants (Yun, 2007).

Materials and Methods. The methodological framework of this study is based on a comprehensive approach that incorporates linguistic, semantic, comparative, and cultural analysis methods.

An etymological analysis was conducted to determine the origin and historical development of the meanings of the lexemes 손님 [sonnim] (“honored guest”) and 고객님 [gogaengnim] (“honored client”). This method enabled us to trace the semantic evolution of these terms and identify their core semantic components.

To examine the current semantic features of the selected lexemes, componential analysis was applied. This method focuses on identifying and describing the minimal semantic features that differentiate the meanings of 손님 [sonnim] and 고객님 [gogaengnim] in contemporary Korean linguoculture.

In order to determine the usage domains and contextual nuances of the lexemes under study, a comparative analysis of language material was employed.

Additionally, contextual analysis was used to refine and demonstrate the specific functions of 손님 [sonnim] and 고객님 [gogaengnim] depending on the particular communicative situation and the nature of the interlocutors' relationship.

Finally, the cultural analysis method was applied to explore the influence of traditional and contemporary Korean cultural values on the selection and preference of specific lexical items. This method also helped interpret the findings from the perspective of the culturally and pragmatically conditioned features of Korean society.

Results and Discussion. Based on the results of the conducted study, the following conclusions have been formulated:

1. In contemporary Korean linguoculture, the lexemes 손님 [sonnim] (“honored guest”) and 고객님 [gogaengnim] (“honored client”) exhibit clear semantic differentiation, which is determined by cultural and social characteristics of communicative interaction.

2. Etymological analysis has shown that the lexeme 손님 [sonnim] is traditionally associated with notions of hospitality, personal relationships, and emotionally nuanced respect. In contrast, 고객님 [gogaengnim] emerged under the influence of market and commercial relations, emphasizing formal and professionally oriented interactions.

3. Comparative and contextual analysis revealed that 손님 [sonnim] is actively used in informal communication contexts that highlight the personal aspect of social relationships, whereas 고객님 [gogaengnim] is preferred in business communication, marketing, and service-related fields, reflecting predominantly formal and status-oriented interaction.

4. It was found that the choice and use of these lexemes in communication is significantly influenced by traditional Korean values (such as respect for the interlocutor, collectivism, and the importance of personal relationships) as well as modern cultural trends. These factors contribute to the consolidation of their distinct pragmatic and cultural connotations.

Thus, the semantic and pragmatic differentiation between 손님 [sonnim] and 고객님 [gogaengnim] clearly reflects the features of the national mentality and cultural specificity of modern Korea, making these lexemes representative markers of the sociocultural identity of Korean language speakers.

The Korean language, as an agglutinative and socioculturally oriented language, provides rich material for the analysis of marked vocabulary. Particular attention is paid to the expression of distance, hierarchy, and politeness, which are realized not only through grammatical forms (e.g., speech levels and honorifics), but also through lexical choice.

One vivid example of this type of differentiation is the opposition between the lexemes 손님 [sonnim] and 고객님 [gogaengnim], which clearly illustrates the transition from traditional hospitality models to the norms of modern business communication. These words reflect the coexistence in the language of elements of cultural heritage—such as respect for elders and warm treatment of guests—and the standards of commercial ethics, which involve a formalized politeness directed at the client as a consumer of services.

The lexeme 손님 [sonnim] originates from the Old Korean word 손 [son], recorded in one of the earliest monuments of Korean writing—“계림유사” [Kyerimyusa]. Initially, 손 [son] meant “guest” or “visitor,” and in later language practice, the honorific suffix -님 [-nim] was added to the base 손 [son], resulting in the form 손님 [sonnim] (“honored guest”), which reflects the traditional respectful attitude toward guests in Korean culture.

The earliest written attestation of the form 손님 [sonnim] in Hangul dates back to 1447, when it appeared in the text “용비어천가” [Yongbieocheonga] (Naver Dictionary, n.d.). One of the passages includes the following: 아바나 | 따 뒤헤 셔샤 赴京 ㅎ · ㄹᄂ 소나 · | 마리 三韓 今日에 엇더 ㅎ · 니 ㅎ | 스고 (“How do you find our country today?” asked the honored guest, traveling to the capital with his father.)

This example illustrates that even in the 15th century, the lexeme 손님 [sonnim] possessed not only a denotative meaning, but also a pronounced connotative sense of respect.

In modern Korean, the lexeme 손님 [sonnim] is predominantly used in everyday and social contexts, referring both to a literal guest in a home and to a visitor in service-related institutions. Its semantics preserve deeply rooted elements of the traditional concept of a guest as a socially significant figure. Pragmatically, the lexeme “guest” reflects a culture of respectful reception, in which the guest is viewed as someone deserving adherence to norms of politeness, ritual modesty, and hospitality.

This is further confirmed by Korean proverbs. For example, the saying 문전 나그네 혼연대접 [munjeon nageune heunyeon daejep] – “Greet the guest who comes to your gate with warmth” – emphasizes the necessity of treating every visitor with equal cordiality regardless of their social status. The idiom 객인환대 / 客人歡待 [gaegin hwandae] – “cordial and sincere reception of a guest” – also points to the ethical obligation of the host to show respect and care. Similarly, the expression 도리영객 / 倒履迎客 [dori yeonggaek] – “putting shoes on backwards to greet a guest” – symbolizes the host’s haste and genuine joy upon the arrival of a respected visitor.

The Korean lexeme 손 [son], meaning “guest,” is also associated with the synonymous Sino-Korean unit 객 / 客 [gaek] – “guest,” “visitor,” or “traveler.” This character is composed of 宀 (roof) and 各 (each, individual), where 各 originally symbolized a foot entering a house. Thus, the lexeme 객 / 客 [gaek] literally denotes “a person entering the house”—that is, a guest. In other cases, it can also carry the meanings “wanderer,” “temporary resident,” “stranger,” or “under protection.”

In the meanings “wanderer” and “traveler,” the Korean language uses the native lexeme 나그네 [nageune], which is an old word recorded in Middle Korean texts. The morpheme 나 [na] in this word form likely derives from a verb stem meaning “to go out, to leave” (cf. 나다 [nada], 나가다 [nagada]).

Therefore, the word 나그네 [nageune] refers to a person who has left their home and is on a journey (Naver Dictionary, n.d.).

Let us analyze proverbs, sayings, and idioms containing these lexemes to identify similarities and differences in their semantic structures.

The idiom 반객위주 / 反客爲主 [bangaekwiju] – “The guest becomes the host” – is used in both written and spoken discourse, particularly in politics, business, and interpersonal relationships. It implies a shift in power or control into the hands of an outsider—for instance, a dependent state dictating terms to a stronger one, or a hired manager taking over the authority of a company’s owner.

The proverb 나그네가 (도리어) 주인 노릇 한다 [nageunega (dori'eo) ju'in noret handa]

– “The guest behaves like the host” – refers to the presumptuous behavior of a guest who oversteps social norms. It is used in everyday situations when someone comes into another’s home and behaves dominantly, or when a new employee acts as if they were already in charge. This proverb reflects Confucian etiquette, which dictates that a guest should be humble. Violation of this rule is seen as socially inappropriate.

The saying 황천의 나그네를 짓다 [hwangcheonui nageunereul jitda] – “to become a guest of the underworld” – is a euphemism for death or the act of passing to the afterlife. For example: 그는 결국 황천의 나그네를 지었다. [geuneun gyeolguk hwangcheonui nageunereul ji'eotda.] “He finally departed for the afterlife.”

The idiom 황양지객 / 黃壤之客 [hwangyangji] – “guest of the yellow earth” – describes a deceased person, emphasizing the finality of death. It is a set euphemism used in formal speech to refer to the dead: 이미 황양지객이 된 사람을 욕하지 마라. [imi hwang-yangjigaegi doen saram-eul yokhaji mara.] “Do not speak ill of someone who has already become a guest of the yellow earth.”

Both expressions convey the concept of death through the image of a traveler. However, the first emphasizes the moment of transition to the afterlife, while the second highlights the deceased person’s status after death.

The proverb 사위는 백년손이라 [sawineun baengnyeonsoonira] – “A son-in-law is a guest for a hundred years” reflects traditional family relationships in Korean culture. In a traditional Korean family, particularly within a Confucian society, the son-in-law (사위 [sawi]) was not regarded as a full-fledged member of the wife’s family but rather as an honored guest who was treated with respect yet kept at a certain distance. This was expressed in the fact that a son-in-law rarely stayed long at his in-laws’ house and was expected to strictly follow etiquette during visits. This expression is rooted in the patriarchal structure, where lineage was preserved through the male line, and daughters, once married, joined their husband’s family.

The idiom 백년지객 / 百年之客 [baengnyeon jigaek] – “a hundred-year guest” is used in Korean culture as a metaphor for a son-in-law (사위 [sawi]), emphasizing his special yet external status within the wife’s family. Although the word “son-in-law” is not directly mentioned, this expression has become established in Korean with this specific meaning. It reflects a traditional Confucian understanding in which the son-in-law, while treated respectfully, was not considered a full member of the wife’s family and remained a “guest” throughout his life. The persistence and frequency of this idiom’s use are attributed to the influence of classical Chinese literature and Confucian philosophy, which similarly emphasize the social distance between the son-in-law and his in-laws.

Both the Korean and Chinese expressions convey a similar idea: the son-in-law is not seen as a full family member but as an outsider whose presence remains external. The Korean expression focuses on family relationships and specifically denotes the son-in-law’s status, while the Chinese idiom has a broader meaning: the lexeme 객 / 客 [gaek] can refer not only to a son-in-law but also to anyone who, despite being part of a community, is not fully integrated and maintains the status of an outsider.

The proverb 장사치의 손님 [jangsachiui sonnim], literally meaning “a merchant’s guest,” reflects a pragmatic attitude characteristic of the professional sphere. According to interpretations found in Korean sources, its meaning is explained as: 심지어 마음에는 없어도 겉으로는

누구에게나 잘 대접한다 – “Even if there is no personal affection, one must treat every visitor well on the outside.”

This highlights that politeness and courtesy in this context are not ethical obligations but strategic tools. Such behavior is not an expression of internal respect, but a means to maintain business reputation and ensure successful client relations.

Thus, hospitality here functions as a pragmatic norm determined by the merchant’s professional role. Even in the absence of genuine sympathy, the seller is obligated to show politeness, as commercial success depends on it.

Accordingly, this proverb represents politeness as a social strategy in which respect for the client stems not from moral duty but from economic necessity. This contrasts with expressions grounded in Confucian ethics, where hospitality is built on sincerity, virtue, and interpersonal harmony.

A comparison with the Chinese idiom 主客之誼 / 주객지의 [jugaekjiui] – “amicable relations between host and guest” reveals a difference in cultural emphasis. In the Chinese-Confucian context, this phrase points to the ethical responsibility of both sides to maintain respectful and harmonious interaction based on ritual observance. Here, politeness functions as a manifestation of virtue rather than a tool of gain.

Thus, while both expressions emphasize the importance of maintaining respectful relations between the receiving and visiting parties, their motivations differ: in the Korean expression, politeness is pragmatic and business-oriented, whereas in the Chinese idiom, it is ethical and moral in nature.

In Korean linguistic culture, warmth and openness toward guests are widely reflected in proverbial expressions. Proverbs and idioms not only describe communicative situations but also transmit stable cultural norms of behavior.

1. 객인환대 / 客人歡待 [gaegin hwandae] – “Cordial and sincere reception of a guest.” This idiom establishes a cultural norm: the host is obliged to receive any visitor with respect and friendliness, regardless of their status.

2. 도리영객 / 倒履迎客 [dori yeonggaek] – “Putting on shoes backward to greet a guest.” This vivid metaphor conveys the host’s rush and joy at the arrival of a long-awaited or honored guest, highlighting the emotional dimension of traditional Korean hospitality.

3. 주주객반 / 主酒客飯 [juju gaekban] – “The host offers wine, the guest brings rice.” This idiom illustrates mutual attention and respect between parties during a reception, emphasizing balance and polite cooperation within a ritual context.

4. 문전 나그네 흔연대접 [munjeon nageune heunyeon daejep] – “Greet the wanderer at your gate with warmth.” This proverb reflects the idea of openness and readiness to welcome anyone, even a stranger. It sets hospitality as a moral obligation.

5. 송작영객개, 월위독서등 [songjak yeonggaekgae, wolwi dokseodeung] – “The pine serves as an umbrella for the guest, the moon as a reading lamp.” A poetic idiom expressing the desire to provide the best possible conditions for a visitor, portraying ideal hospitality in which even nature partakes in caring for the guest.

6. 큰 쌀독 열어 놓고 손님 대접한다 [keun ssaldok yeoreo nokko sonnim daejeop handa] – “Serve the guest by opening the big rice jar.” This proverb symbolizes generous hospitality and sincere treatment of the guest, even if it requires significant effort or expense from the host.

7. 이웃집 나그네도 손볼 날이 있다 [iutjip nageunedo sonbol nari itda] – “One day you will also have to receive a wanderer from the neighboring house.” This phrase emphasizes that anyone may find themselves in the position of a guest, and respectful treatment should be universal and not selective.

Thus, analysis of proverbs with the lexemes 손 [son] (“guest”), 객 [gaek] (“guest,” “visitor”), and 나그네 [nageune] (“wanderer,” “traveler”) shows that the cultural specificity and origin of these units allow for the transmission of not only subtle semantic nuances but also diverse contextual and emotional shades. The usage patterns of these lexemes in Korean paremiology demonstrate how Korean ethnocultural perspectives are reflected in language through stylistic distinctions and contextual applications, emphasizing the importance of social roles and traditional norms of etiquette.

The modern lexeme 고객님 [gogaengnim] (“honored client”) has a relatively recent origin and is a compound word of Sino-Korean origin. It is derived from 客 [gaek] meaning “guest” and 顧 [go] meaning “to care for” or “to pay attention to,” which together form 고객 [gogaek], meaning “client” or “customer” (Naver Dictionary, n.d.). The addition of the honorific suffix -님 [-nim] adds a formal and polite nuance. Thus, 고객님 [gogaengnim] literally means “honored client” and serves as a prime example of linguistic etiquette in contemporary business and service communication.

This lexeme is widely used in formal and commercial interactions—in banks, retail stores, internet services, telecommunications, and more. Salespeople, customer service agents, and company representatives commonly address consumers as 고객님 [gogaengnim], demonstrating respect within the established norms of business etiquette. Unlike 손님 [sonnim], which carries a warmer and more personal tone, 고객님 [gogaengnim] has a distinctly professional and institutional connotation and is not typically associated with private relationships.

Stylistically, 고객님 [gogaengnim] belongs to the formal-polite register and reflects the elevated status of the customer as a service recipient in modern society. Its use is integral to marketing and communication strategies aimed at expressing respect, care, and a personalized approach on behalf of the company.

The lexemes 손님 [sonnim] and 고객님 [gogaengnim] function as partial synonyms in modern Korean but differ significantly in meaning, usage, and pragmatic context. Both refer to an individual entering into a social interaction, yet their stylistic coloring and communicative roles are distinct.

The similarities lie in their core semantics—they both designate a person seeking service or engaging in interpersonal interaction within someone else's domain (e.g., home, institution, platform). Both include the honorific suffix -님 [-nim], emphasizing respectful address. However, their semantic and pragmatic differentiation becomes evident depending on context.

The lexeme 손님 [sonnim] is traditionally associated with a guest in a domestic, informal, or cultural setting. It is used in situations emphasizing human relationships, hospitality, and respect. In digital contexts, 손님 [sonnim] is commonly applied to services that allow temporary or unregistered participation.

For instance, in Cisco Webex Meetings, users can join a conference as 손님으로 참여 [sonnimeuro chamyeo]—“join as a guest” (Webex Help Center, n.d.).

In gaming platforms such as Xbox, temporary user profiles are created under the label 손님 [sonnim]: 손님으로 로그인하고 게임을 시작합니다 [Sonnimeuro rogeuinhago geimeul sijakhamnida] – “Sign in as a guest and start the game” (Select from User Blog, n.d.).

In Google Chrome, incognito mode is referred to as 게스트 모드 [geseu-teu modeu]— “guest mode”: 손님 모드에서는 기록이 저장되지 않습니다 [Sonnim modeuseoneun girogi jeojangdoeji anseumnida] – “Browsing history is not saved in guest mode” (Google Support, n.d.).

On forums and in online chats, unauthenticated users are automatically labeled 손님 [sonnim], which preserves a level of respect even for anonymous participants (Naver Blog, n.d.).

Additionally, 손님 [sonnim] is frequently used in marketing language to emphasize building lasting relationships: 뜨내기 손님을 단골 손님으로 만드는 것이 중요합니다 [Tteunaegi sonnimeul dangol sonnim-euro mandeuneun geosi jungyohamnida] – “It is important to turn a passing guest into a regular one” (ZDNet Korea, n.d.).

In contrast, 고객님 [gogaengnim] is used predominantly in formal and commercial environments. The term is prevalent in marketing, banking, insurance, online shopping, and mobile applications. For instance, online stores often address customers with: 고객님, 주문해 주셔서 감사합니다 [Gogaengnim, jumunhae jusyeoseo gamsahamnida] – “Dear customer, thank you for your order” (Naver Blog, n.d.; Select from User Blog, n.d.).

In food delivery apps (e.g., Baemin): 고객님, 주문이 접수되었습니다 [Gogaengnim, jumuni jeopsudoeetsseumnida] – “Dear customer, your order has been received.”

In business communication: 고객님들의 소중한 의견을 반영하겠습니다 [Gogaengnimdeurui sojunghan uigyuneul banyonghagetsseumnida] – “We will reflect the valuable opinions of our esteemed clients” (Select from User Blog, n.d.).

Thus, 손님 [sonnim] is a lexeme with a warm, culturally marked semantic range associated with the concept of hospitality and interpersonal etiquette, whereas 고객님 [gogaengnim] represents the formal discourse of modern business communication, where individuals are primarily viewed as consumers.

The social factors influencing the choice between these lexemes depend on the level of formality, communicative goals, the nature of the interaction (private or professional), and the desired degree of interpersonal distance. 손님 [sonnim] emphasizes the personal dimension, while 고객님 [gogaengnim] highlights the institutional.

For example, in a small restaurant, a waiter may address a visitor as: 손님, 뭐 도와드릴까요? [Sonnim, mwo dowadeurilkayo?] – “Dear guest, how may I help you?” Whereas in an online store, the phrasing might be: 고객님, 무엇을 찾고 계신가요? [Gogaengnim, mueoseul chatgo gyesingayo?] – “Dear customer, what are you looking for?”

Examples from digital environments demonstrate that both lexemes remain relevant, but serve different communicative functions: 손님 [sonnim]—a means of expressing respect in social and everyday contexts; 고객님 [gogaengnim]—a formalized marker of corporate politeness. This supports the trend of differentiated politeness based on communicative context.

In conclusion, comparative analysis reveals that 손님 [sonnim] and 고객님 [gogaengnim] are not merely synonyms but lexemes that fulfill distinct cultural-pragmatic functions within the framework of contemporary Korean linguistic culture.

Conclusion. The lexical-semantic distinction between the lexemes 손님 [sonnim] and

고객님 [gogaengnim] is closely tied to the cultural and pragmatic orientations of Korean society. These orientations have been shaped by the influence of traditional Confucian ethics and contemporary norms of business communication, which have significantly impacted both the meaning and the usage of these lexemes.

In traditional Korean culture, the guest was perceived as a socially significant figure who deserved respect, hospitality, and politeness regardless of social status. Within this context, 손님 [sonnim] acquired strong cultural markedness: beyond its nominative meaning of “guest,” it carries stable socio-ethical connotations related to ritual behavior and the hierarchical nature of interpersonal relationships. The guest is conceptualized as a temporary but honored participant in communication, toward whom specific norms of speech and behavioral etiquette are expected.

In contrast, 고객님 [gogaengnim] has become established in the sphere of formal, business, and service-oriented communication. It does not reflect a personal relationship but rather an institutional role—that of a service recipient. Its use is governed by the pragmatics of polite service and the norms of market-based interaction. This lexeme represents a modern model of communication grounded in the principles of contract-based interaction and customer orientation.

The comparative analysis demonstrates that 손님 [sonnim] and 고객님 [gogaengnim] are not full synonyms: they fulfill distinct cultural-pragmatic functions. The former maintains a connection with Confucian values and the traditional notion of a guest, while the latter is embedded in the discourse of the modern economy, where the key elements are service standards and professional politeness.

Therefore, the distinction between these lexemes reflects not only lexical-semantic variation but also a deeper cultural differentiation—one that mirrors the evolving concepts of “guest” and “client” in contemporary Korean linguistic culture and society.

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